

Spectrophotometric determination of palladium(II) using 2-cis 3,7-dimethyl 2,6-octadien-1-oxime

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2-cis 3,7-Dimethyl 2,6-octadien-1-oxime forms a 1 : 2 (Pd : CDOO) red coloured complex at 47–57° in 0.03–0.14 M CH₃COOH medium which is extracted into chloroform having a λ_{\max} at 445 nm. The molar absorptivity, Sandell's sensitivity and standard deviations are $2.434 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $0.0007 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and ± 0.0012 absorbance unit respectively. Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range 0.4–40.0 mg/ml of Pd^{II}. Presence of a large number of elements do not interfere. The method has good reproducibility and can be satisfactorily applied for the analysis of industrial samples.

Liu *et al.*¹ have reviewed a new system for simultaneous spectrophotometric determination of platinum(IV) and palladium(II). A survey of literature reveals that a large number of reagents, such as oxime^{2,3}, semicarbazone and thiosemicarbazones^{4,5} have been reported for determination of Pd^{II}. Spectrophotometric methods coupled with a separation technique like solvent extraction can be advantageously applied for the determination of metal at low concentrations^{6,7}. In the present investigation, 2-cis 3,7-dimethyl 2,6-octadien-1-oxime has been used as a sensitive spectrophotometric reagent for the determination of palladium(II). Formation of coloured complex form the basis of a sensitive spectrophotometric method of determination of Pd^{II} in trace amounts offering high selectivity and reproducibility in the analysis. The reagent is very typical and specific in the sense that it is an oxime derivative of acyclic monoterpenoid from lemon grass oil.

Results and discussion

2-cis 3,7-Dimethyl 2,6-octadien-1-oxime forms a soluble red coloured 1 : 2 complex with Pd^{II}. The extraction of 500 μg of Pd^{II} was carried out at different pH keeping aqueous to organic volume ratio 1 : 2. The extraction behaviour of Pd^{II} in chloroform as function of pH was found to be as follows : %Extraction 64.48, 70.44, 78.41, 100.00, 86.97, 89.44, 90.39, 91.87, 8.88, 77.74 and corresponding distribution ratio 0.83, 2.40, 3.66, ∞ , 6.24, 8.81, 9.72, 11.05, 5.05, 3.09 at pH 1.0–10.0 respectively. The extraction was found to be quantitative at pH 4.0. Solution become turbid after the pH 10.

The absorption of this complex in chloroform showed λ_{\max} around 445 nm. Beer's law was obeyed over the concentration range 0.4–40.0 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-3}$ of Pd^{II}. Molar absorptivity of the extraction species was $2.43 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3$

$\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The concentration of reagent was varied from 0.1 to 5.0 keeping aqueous to organic ratio 1 : 2. It was found that 2.0 ml of 2% reagent in ethanol was needed for quantitative extraction of the metal ion. In the general procedure 5.0 ml of 2% reagent is recommended to ensure complete extraction of metal ions. The extraction behaviour of Pd^{II} in chloroform as a function of equilibrium time was found to be as follows :

Time	0.25	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	5.0	10.0
A	0.2131	0.4060	0.5172	0.6194	0.8383	0.8335	0.8340
Extraction (%)	37.53	49.02	62.52	83.81	99.95	99.92	99.91

A minimum period of 2 min equilibrium time was found adequate for quantitative extraction of Pd^{II}. The colour of the complex was found to remain stable for 72 h at room temperature.

The effect of some ions that often associate with Pd^{II} was studied by adding different ammoniates to 500 μg of Pd^{II} solution. An error $\pm 3\%$ in the absorbance reading is considered tolerable. The tolerance limits (mg) of various ions were found to be as follows : Na, K Ca^{II}, Sr^{II}, SO₄²⁻ (25); As^{III} (16); Ba^{II}, Mn^{II}, Al^{III} (10); Mg^{II}, Hg^{II} (9.5); nitrate, iodate, chlorate, acetate, fluoride, chloride, bromide (10).

Synthetic mixture corresponding to the Pd-Fe, Pd-Ni and Pd-Zn alloy of different composition were prepared and the palladium contents were determined by the proposed method and the relative errors were found to be 0.204, -0.502, and 0.251%, respectively out of 5 determinations. The relative error of Pd^{II} was found to be -0.20 and -1.0% in standard samples like silver alloys and Pd-charcoal catalyst, respectively.

The optimum values of other parameters found for achieving maximum and constant absorbance were 125–250 mg sodium dithionite, 0.03–0.14 M acetic acid media, 0.6–1.3 ml of 0.05% w/v oxime solution in ethanol for $\leq 8.5 \mu\text{Pd}^{\text{II}}$ per 10 ml aqueous solution mentioned at 47–57° and equilibrating once with an equal volume of chloroform for 12–300 s at room temperature (25°). The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were $7.45 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0007 \mu\text{g cm}^2$ respectively at 445 nm. The standard deviation was ± 0.0012 absorbance limit.

Conclusions : The reagent provides a simple, rapid and accurate method for the spectrophotometric determination of Pd^{II} . The reagent has the advantage of high sensitivity, selectivity and easy availability. The accuracy of the method is comparable with most methods reported in the literature. Most of the common metal ions, which are associated with palladium either in mineral or in alloys, do not interfere in its determination and hence the method can be used for the analysis of alloys, minerals, artificial mixtures and standard sample mixtures for their palladium content.

Experimental

All the reagents were of A.R. grade. The present investigation describes extractive spectrophotometric determination of Pd^{II} in aqueous solution using 2-*cis* 3,7-dimethyl 2,6-octadien-1-oxime as a reagent and chloroform as an extractive solvent.

Standard stock solution (1.0 mg/ml) was prepared by dissolving palladium chloride (A.R.) in 0.5 M HCl (A.R.) and standardized gravimetrically⁸. It was then suitably diluted to prepare the standard solutions.

2-*cis* 3,7-Dimethyl 2,6-octadien-1-oxime was prepared⁹ by the condensation of 2-*cis* 3,7-dimethyl 2,6-octadien-1-al and hydroxylamine hydrochloride. It was characterized by elemental analysis, IR and NMR spectral data. Buffer solutions of suitable pH were prepared by mixing borax,

potassium hydrogen phthalate, potassium dihydrogen phosphate, KCl, HCl and NaOH in proper proportion¹⁰.

A Baush and Lomb spectronic-20 spectrophotometer and an Elico LI-120 pH meter were used.

Procedure : To aliquot of the stock solution containing 500 μg of Pd^{II} was added 2% ethanolic solution of 2-*cis* 3,7-dimethyl 2,6-octadien-1-oxime (15 ml) and made up to 25 ml using buffer solution of pH 4.0. The solution were then shaken and the absorbance was measured at 445 nm against the reagent blank.

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